

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B262
 Date: 25 January 2007
 Take Off 10:03:16 16:25:02
 Landing: 15:24:15 17:01:58
 Flight Time 5h20m59 0h36m56

Campaign: WINTEX – CAESAR

Operating Area: N Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Claire Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
6	AVAPS / Core Chem	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist 2	Jon Taylor	Met Office
9	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
10	MARSS	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
11	SWS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
12	Flight Manager Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
13	TAFTS	Paul Green	Imperial College
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B262 Track 25-JAN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b262
 Date: 25 January 2007
 Project: CAESAR
 Location: N. SEA

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
094633		Start-Up	-.05 kft	111	52'04.36 N 0'37.50 W
100316		T/O	0.79 kft	126	
100701		ASP	5.0 kft	047	ASP opened
110500		Video	19.0 kft	012	Start Recording
111114	113207	Profile 1	19.0 - -.29 kft	011	Profile ended @ 50ft
113208	114733	Run 1	-.29 - -.16 kft	338	qh1022 100ft run
113304		Video	-.22 kft	339	RFC to UFC
114733	121226	Profile 2	-.16 - 5.0 kft	338	100ft to 5000ft
114842		Video	0.72 kft	338	UFC to RFC
115922		Video	8.9 kft	159	FFC to DFC
121534	123046	Run 2	21.1 - 21.0 kft	023	RUN 2.1
123142		Video	21.0 kft	065	Tapes changed
123317	124112	Run 2.2	21.1 - 21.0 kft	203	
124000		Sonde	21.0 kft	162	launch sonde 1
124112	125020	Profile 3	21.0 - 30.0 kft	162	
125915	131243	Run 3	30.0 - 30.3 kft	346	
131243	131633	Profile 4	30.3 - 32.0 kft	342	
131613	131648	Run 4	32.0 kft	343	
131648	131831	Profile 5	32.2 - 33.0 kft	342	
132241	132355	Profile 6	33.0 - 34.0 kft	141	
132507	132741	Profile 7	34.0 - 35.0 kft	148	
132741	135235	Run 5	35.0 kft	161	
133007		Sonde	35.0 kft	158	launch sonde 2
133518		Sonde	35.0 kft	161	launch sonde 3
133628		event	35.0 kft	174	shallow turn
134212		event	35.0 kft	009	hard turn
134648		event	35.1 kft	358	back on track SLR
135235	140831	Profile 8	35.0 - 20.0 kft	344	
140005		Video	28.0 kft	343	Tapes changed
141358	143036	Profile 9	20.0 - 35.0 kft	163	
143036	144522	Profile 10	35.0 - 20.1 kft	208	During turn
144522	144959	Profile 11	20.1 - 24.0 kft	257	
145000	150756	Run 6	24.0 kft	258	Transit
151515		ASP	9.7 kft	081	ASP closed
152415		Land	-.11 kft	245	Newcastle
152740		Event	-.11 kft	190	55'02.00 1'41.93

B262 Track 25-JAN-07

CAESAR Sortie Brief

B262 25/01/07

Radar validation and intercomparison of cirrus microphysics

Aim:

The aim of this sortie is to obtain a good statistical representation of the in-situ microphysics of a frontal or convective cirrus case, which is coincident with radar measurements from CloudSat. Measurements should be made between fixed ground points on the sub-satellite track. The footprint of the CloudSat radar is 1.4km (across track) x 2.5km (along track). A few runs above and below the cloud are to be made for radiative measurements, in addition to the saw tooth manoeuvres for the in-situ measurements.

Weather conditions:

Frontal cirrus, ideally with clear skies below. It is essential to be able to get just above the cirrus. Small amounts of low cloud are acceptable if they are measurable by the radar.

Location:

North Sea (under CloudSat suborbital track).

Clearances:

NOTAMS will be required for dropping sondes.

Instruments required:

Critical: SID1, 2DC, 2DP, CDP, Temp, Humidity

Desirable: SID2, CIPs, AVAPS, ARIES, SWS, MARSS, TAFTS, SHIMS, Heimann, Core chem (automatic mode acceptable)

Way points

point A: 56° 43.2'N, 3°30'E

point B: 57°1.2'N, 3°15'E

point C: 58°8.2'N, 2°36'E

point D: 58°34.4'N, 2°20'E

		Manoeuvre	Duration (min)
1	1000Z	Takeoff from Cranfield. Transit to point A	45
2	1045Z	Profile descent to point B 50ft above sea	30
3	1115Z	Straight and level run from B to C at 100ft	15
4	1130Z	Profile ascent (from C to D to A) to 1000ft below Ci base	25
5	1155Z	Straight and level run from A to D 1000ft below Ci base	20
6	1215Z	Perform a series of ascending and descending profiles in a saw tooth pattern through the cirrus to an altitude of 1000ft above (or max poss) and below the cloud respectively, along or perpendicular to the wind, covering fixed ground positions D-A.	20
7	1235Z	Interrupt saw tooth at 1000ft above Ci. Drop 1 sonde during satellite overpass (1240)	10
8	1245Z	Continue series of ascending and descending profiles ending at D	55
9	1340Z	2 straight & level runs 1000ft above cloud - D to A to D. Drop 2 sondes in 1 st run separated by 5 mins.	40
10	1420Z	Profile descent to transit altitude from D to A	20
11	1440Z	Transit to Newcastle	30
12	1510Z	Land at Newcastle	Total 310
13		Refuel & transit to Cranfield	

CLOUDSAT 2007/01/09 UTC CLOUDSAT ORBITAL PREDICT PLOT EPOCH DATE: 07/01/03
 ■ lat: 51.57 lon: 358.69 res: 9 km

Additional requirement:

Observation of contrail presence or absence behind aircraft.

The aim is to acquire data that can be used to provide additional validation of a new contrail prediction algorithm that is being developed for defence customer use.

Weather conditions: No special conditions required but contrail formation is unlikely at temperatures warmer than about -45 degC.

Manoeuvres: No special manoeuvres required.

Special instrument instructions: When operating below -45 degC, the video-recording should be switched to include the rear-facing camera, unless otherwise required by the main mission science. Mission scientist 2 should monitor the video display and record log entries for both presence *and absence* of contrails behind the aircraft.

Instrument operator instructions:

ARIES and SWS

- Both instruments must point in the same direction as each other (except during cal).
ARIES needs to tell SWS where it is pointing.
- Majority of time should be towards the cloud (or sea at 100ft)
- However, still need some data pointing away to characterise the atmosphere above and below the cloud (e.g. ~2 mins of 10 min run)

SWS

- Zenith = 6 deg forward

Mission Scientist Debrief

B262 25/1/07 North-East North Sea CAESAR sortie – CloudSat validation

Mission scientist – Clare Lee

Summary

A reasonably successful in-situ cirrus flight for validation of CloudSat, with remote sensing runs above and below the cirrus. The cirrus was layered - not an ideal homogenous band, with some StCu below. Contrails were monitored.

Weather Conditions

At the start of the flight the cirrus was thin, with some StCu below. The StCu was patchy with cloud tops and bases between 2 – 3 kft, and 3.5 – 5 kft, and consisted of wet snow. The cirrus was thinner and higher at the Southern end of the track. The cirrus thickened throughout the flight, with variable amounts of StCu dependent on location and time. There were multiple layers of cirrus and was inhomogeneous throughout the flight with variable cloud tops and bases (approx 21 - 35.5 kft).

Contrails were observed both above approx. 21 kft and at lower moisture layers. Engine settings and times were noted – see end of debrief.

Location

Eastern edge of the North Sea under the CloudSat suborbital track, from point A (Southern end) to point D (Northern end). Note this area was particularly hard to work in as on several occasions we lost audible contact with air traffic and airways crossed the flight track. A refuel was made at Newcastle.

Sortie

A profile descent from FL190 to 50ft was made towards point A with a gradual turn to the North to be on the A to D track after the transit. A 100ft run over the sea was made in the same direction (B to C). With a wind of 4 ms⁻¹ there were sea waves, but no white caps (force 2). The Cu was patchy with thin Ci above. An attempt was made to have ARIES viewing zenith during the clear slots between the banded Cu. An interrupted profile ascent to FL220 was made, initially heading towards D then on the reciprocal heading. The Heimann is sensitive to the Cu and can be utilised to identify clear slots rather than using the video camera. Ice crystals were observed at FL220, so a descent was made to FL210 for a run under the cirrus. During this run ice crystals were detected falling out of the cirrus, and at certain locations from touching the Ci bases. At some points on the track there was also a lower thin layer of cirrus. The run ended 10 minutes before the satellite overpass time, so the sortie was adjusted such that the aircraft maintained straight and level to enable a sonde to be launched at the overpass time. A profile ascent was then made as part of the saw tooth manoeuvre from FL210 to FL300. This was interrupted at several levels due to air traffic, hence straight and level runs were made whilst waiting for permissions. During the run at FL350 in the very tops of the Ci 2 drop sondes were launched with a 5minute

separation. A slow turn was made for the reciprocal track to ensure that the aircraft could maintain contact with the sonde. In the reciprocal run SWS was having difficulty turning the pointing optics. A profile descent from FL350 to FL200 (approximately 1000ft below cloud base) was made followed by an ascent to FL350. Some small particles were still being measured at the maximum altitude. The last profile descent was made with a small banking angle such that the aircraft remained at point A, ready for the transit to Newcastle. A profile ascent was made to get to the transit altitude (FL240) followed by a run at FL240, but this was not along the sub-satellite track.

Instrument status

PCASP – effected by SWS motor

FFSSP – not fitted

2DP – noisy at high alts

SWS – frozen solid (or physically contracted too much) at high alts ($T < -60C$), even with heating from motor

TAFTS – still has some issues with the laser fringe counts. May be possible to retrieve some data.

ARIES – OK

MARSS – OK, except ch 16

AVAPS – OK. Sonde 2 lost GPS (no wind data)

TW – bad

Aircraft GPS – sky map couldn't fix position for approx 30 mins

Contrails

Time ON	Off	Altitude	Mano-uvre	strength	N1	TGT	N2	FF/FU
11:18	11:19:20	FL110	descent	thin				
11:56	intermittent	FL057	ascent	thin				
12:15	intermittent in turn	FL210	S & L	thin				
12:21	12:25:58	FL210	S & L	thin	78.1	56.8	82.7	4.3
12:26:50	12:37:10	FL210	S & L	thin	78.4	62.7	83.4	4.6
12:38	12:41:12	FL210	S & L	very thin	76.0	60.5	82.2	4.2
12:44	12:45:10	FL243 – FL252	ascent	very thin	94.8	76.4	91.5	7.0
12:48	13:08	FL280 – FL300	ascent	think w/wake	84.4	64.2	85.1	4.3
13:08		FL300	S & L	thin section				
13:08:20	14:00:00	FL300 - FL350 - FL280	ascent & descent	thick	92.8	70.4	88.1	4.7
14:01:10		FL270	descent	none	64.5	60.2	78.3	2.8
14:22:00		FL293	ascent	faint	95.5	75.5	90.5	6.1
14:22:45	14:30:37	FL300 –	ascent	strong	95.8	75.3	90.1	5.8

		FL350						
14:30:37	14:38:35	FL350 – FL275	descent	strong	70.7	58.7	79.6	3.1
14:44	14:45	FL210	descent	very thin, weak wake				

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.262** Date **25/1/07** Name **CLARE LEE** Page **1** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
100412					T10 Cranfield
		FL150			Transit to A.
					W upto ~ 3kft. patches
					varying 1/8 → 3/8
					3/8 Ci above.
1030		FL190	51		Transit to A at higher alt.
1049	Took 2 photos				sidewindow + forward in transit to A
					StW below - thickening as heading towards A, Ci 7/8 → 8/8.
					still quite thin. T = -25°, T ₀ = -40°C
1057					Photo of glory.
1107					Photo at front
					StW breaking, also Ci patchier.
1110					RASP high (noisy) - high alt.
					note some parts probe off though!
11114	PI ↓	FL190	11	55°42'N 3°12'E	Profile descent [↖] effected by SLS meter.
					wind 21ms ⁻¹ 114deg.
					2nd layer cloud above low StW.
					only at ~ 55°54'N, 3°12'E
					wasn't here earlier.
111729					StW cloud nearly 8/8 ahead + slightly thicker.
					~ FL140 → FL100 moist layer
Contrails ~ 1040		FL110			FL110 seen contrails - see RFC.
				56°30'N 3°24'E	6500 → 6000ft → moist layer.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.262** Date **25/1/07** Name **CARE LEE** Page **2** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
112516		5600ft.			Over point A
					turning left onto A→B line.
		5120			moist layer started.
112744		3200	338		In cloud. some turbulence.
112908		2000ft.			Out cloud. snow (wet) no drops TW not sharing
					Clear below 1022 Q+H.
113207	P1 end	50ft.	340		Profile end (still moist at 1000ft.)
113208	R1	100ft.	338	56°054'N 3°12'E	Run naraco. camera VTC.
113255					ARIES + SWS nadir
					wind 6ms - 1283°
					no white caps on sea
					Force 2 using state of sea booklet.
					W 1/8 → 2/8 } above
					Li thin ~ 6/8 → 7/8 } aircraft.
113605					ARIES + Hermon Cal
113945					Was clear of W slot now
					under banded structure of W.
					clear slot ahead.
114301					ARIES + Hermon Cal. Zmms.
114403					Not so much W anymore.
114538					In W ARIES ↑ for Zmms
114606					Thick patch W.
114733	P2↑	100ft.	338		Profile heading towards D.
					W bases ~ 3500ft at
					Northern end.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.262** Date **25/1/07** Name **CLARE LEE** Page **3** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
115341	P2 int.	5000ft.			Showing moist layer ~ 4000ft Profile intercept. turning right. 7/8 → 8/8 Ci looks thin
115537	P2 rec.	5000ft.	194	58° 06' N / 2° 42' E	recommence profile. Thinner Ci to right (West) dry at ~ 5500ft.
115936	P2 int.	9000ft.			Intercepting with due to air traffic.
120205	P2 rec.	9000ft.	163		recommencing. DFC + RFC. note can also use Heimann to check for cloud below.
		FL220			moist 21640. also seeing particles -grapel. → on Ethel physics.
121226	P2 rec.	FL220			turning right between pt. A+B for reciprocal. + dipping to FL210
121534	P2	FL210	027	56	Run below cirrus base 2DP showing fall at low Ci
121736					ARIES looking up.
122031					Going into Ci haze.
1223					Out Ci
122840					In Ci
~1230					Out Ci
					Note thin layer Ci below ~ 1225 - can see signature on Heimann

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.262** Date **25/1/07** Name **CLARE LEE** Page **4** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
123046	R2nd	FL210			End run turning right
123317	R2.2	FL210	206		Start reciprocal heading. 1/2 way between C + B.
123442		FL210	164		In Ci - ice crystals.
123520					Out cloud. Still thin Ci below. (~FL200)
					~ 7/8 W.
123934		FL210			8/8 Ci above. 3/8 W below. no Ci layer below
124000		FL210	162	57°6'N / 3°6'E	Sonde dropped.
124050					In cloud.
124110					Out cloud.
124112	R2 2nd				Profiling End run.
124112	P3↑				Profiling for saw tooth manoeuvre. Some particles as pingy though patches of Ci
124454		~FL250	161		clear gap. Ci thinner + higher at pt. A
124825					Sonde 1 landed.
		FL290			Right turn.
		FL300			Intercept. turn.
					Cloud phys 2DC 10-70µm. 800µm max size graupel ~100µm?
		FL300			Due to air traffic having to stay level.
125451		FL300			Out cloud.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** 262 Date 25/1/07 Name CLARE LEE Page 5 of 9

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125906					In cloud - cloud phys seems patchy
125915					
125920	R3	FL300	34		Rn as can't get permission to change altitude.
130037					low concs.
130431					At dad?
131243	P4	FL300	342		Profile ↑ now get permission. cloud phys. size seems to be decreasing 200 → 300 ft/m
	P4int	FL300			Interpreting profile (max allowable alt at present.)
	R4	FL320			Rn forwards D.
	P5↑	FL330			Now ^{have} permission to climb
131835?	P5ad.	FL330			Still in cloud (max allowable alt at present) turned around.
132241	P6↑	FL330	141		now permission to go higher.
132355	P6int	FL340	138		In tops of cloud. No ZDC. SID _s = high concs.
1325	P7↑	FL340			
132741	P7ad	FL350			End profile at max alt.
13274	R5	FL350	156		towards A.
					Still in cloud.
133007	S2	FL350		57°12'N 3°0'E	Smoke stopped. T = -65.18 → T ₀ = -64.5 wind 19ms ⁻¹ / 352 deg. Still in cloud.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.262** Date **25/1/06** Name **CLARE LEE** Page **6** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133518	S3	FL350	161		Seede dropped near to A Still in cloud.
133608					Slow turn to right so can maintain Seede contact
133943					Out of cloud. Thin layer below.
134204					Steeper turn now dispende 13 km.
134248					Seede slash down.
1342					In cloud.
					SWS having difficulty forming seeds.
134700	R	FL350			Seede on now on track.
134817					Seede 3 slash down
134825					ARRIES radar
					SWS striking. - frozen solid.
					T = -64.7, T _D = -65.7
135235	R5 _{end}	FL350			wind 30ms ⁻¹ 1352°
135235	P8J	FL350	344		Profiling down for in-situ All in Ci much thicker than earlier particularly to N (pt. D)
		FL246			Still in cloud.
					low conc. ZDC ~20 → 30
					SID ~60 small ice + graupel
1405		FL228			Can easily see sea + low W.
					ZDC 40 → 60 conc. graupel.
					lower StW in distinct line high to N.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.262** Date **25/1/07** Name **CLARE LEE** Page **7** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
140650		FL213	342	58°12'N/ 2°30'E	Overcloud - no particles. can see dipping at on top.
140831	P8 end	FL200	341		End profile. Turning left for reciprocal.
141140		FL200	134	58°01'N/ 2°35'E	4 photos taken at point C looking S towards A. ARIES + SWS zenith
141358	P9 ↑	FL 200 ²⁰⁰	162		New permission to FL350.
141505		FL214		57°48'N/ 2°42'E	In cloud. Can see sun blurred by Ci 8/8 W below.
142619					Also now much thicker Ci at S. end (towards pt. A) No gaps as seen before
142800		FL335			Coming towards top Ci
142820					slight turn to right, bank ~ 8°
143036	P9 end	FL350			End profile SIDs seeing small particles no 2D particles.
143147	P10 ↓	FL350			Profile descent with 25° banking angle to right so that at pt. A before transit.
143500		FL310			2DC showing larger particles.
143650		FL271			grayed.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.262** Date **23/1/07** Name **CLARE LEE** Page **8** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144040		FL255			At cloud. Note lower layer thin Ci below, 8/12 ⁵ W below.
144120			275		profiling down at heading towards Newcastle.
1443					Photo taken at aft left window.
144450		FL205			In lower level of Ci
144509		FL202			In cloud.
144522	P10 _{end}	FL200	257		E
144522	P11 ↑	FL200			
144545		FL203			Out of cloud. (visible by eye)
144644		FL212			Out of cloud by cloud physics wind 2ms ⁻¹ / 352°.
					T = -31.6 → T ₀ = -31.8°C
144822		FL220			7/8 W, 7/8 Ci
144959	P11 _{end}	FL240			Profile end at transit alt.
144959	R6	FL240			Running towards Newcastle with SWST ACIES doing with thinning Ci above.
1500					6/8 thin layer below aircraft. C1000ft thick.
					W broken 6/8 below.
					Ci above thinning towards Newcastle. → lower layer more 18/13, but still thin.
150756	R6 _{end}	FL240	242	55° 18' N / 0° 42' W	End science.

Small
turbulence
in clear
sky
area.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.262** Date 25/1/07 Name CLARE LEE Page 9 of 9

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Land at Newcastle for refuel.
					<u>Inst. status.</u>
					TAFS - problems with laser
					ants - should be able to retrieve some data.
					ARIES - OK
					SWS - OK. Frozen at -60 -ve. can't turn.
					Cloud physics - PUPSP noisy
					When SWS motor on. No PUPSP on board.
					2DP noisy at high level.
					AVAPS - OK (and sensor no GPS (winds))
					Core - tw bad. Interference on leaded.
					MASS - OK except ch16.
					Aircraft ^{sky map.} GPS can't fix position.

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 262** Date **25/1/07** Operat or(s) **JEFF BROWN** log page **1** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
0830			140°A	1000		All OK AFTER SYSTEM STARTUP	✓		
0830			140°A	750		All OK		✓	
0830			140°A	1000		LSH "Stick" required reset towards			✓
0844			140°A			All returned to flatline unless			
0844						individually "darked"			
093102		0	140°A			Scene on - all O.K.	✓	✓	✓
093802		0	140°A	400		Scene on for upper shims.		✓	
094730		0	140°A			All dark for check - all ok.	✓	✓	✓
100434		1100	140°A			All scene after T/O	✓	✓	✓
100556		3900	6° F	750		Head moved to Zenith. All	✓		
////				250		int times adjusted. Ci		✓	✓
////				1000		above. Transit through 2/8 Cu 1			✓
102340		15000	6° F			Above 5/8 SCS (below thin Ci)	✓	✓	✓
102907		17000	6° F	300		Adjusted as we cross coast to Sea.			✓
////						4/8 Cu 1			
103922		19000	6° F	400		Scene selected after Int adjust	✓		
104612		19000		750		Dark all during int adjust	✓		
104633		19000	6° F	750		Scene all during int adjust			✓
105054		19000	6° F	500		Dark as under Ci	✓		
105130		19000	6° F	500		Scene during int adjust	✓		
105430		19000	6° F	500		Dark during int adjust			✓
105455		19000	6° F	500		Scene during int adjust			✓
////						over SCS (6/8)			
105455		19000	6° F			Clear of SCS			
110809		19000	6° F	350		Dark all during int adjust	✓		
110845		19000	6° F	350		Scene all during int adjust			✓
////						Ci2 above SCS below			
111115	P1	19000				Profile descent			
111334	P1	17000	6° F	750		Int adjust during descent	✓		
111401	P1			750		Scene all			✓
* SWS DRIVER MOTOR AFFECTING 2) PCASP *									
112325	P1	7000	7000 6°A	600		Int adjust whilst transit	✓		
112347	P1	6500	6500 6°A	400		SCS. Scene selected	✓		
113207	P1	50				Start of run end of profile			
113208	R1.1	100	174°A			Head to Nadir.			
113328	R1.1	100	174°A	1000		Dark all	✓		
113250	R1.1	100	174°A	1000		Scene all			✓
113417	R1.1	100	174°A	1000		Scene for LSH as held			✓
114530	R1.1	100	6° F			Head to Zenith			
114538	R1.1	100	6° F	500		Dark at SWS	✓		
114600	R1.1	100	6° F	500		Scene at SWS	✓		
114733	P2	100	174° 6° F			End of run. Start of Profile			
114805	P2	300	174°A			Head to Zenith Nadir			
114842	P2	800	174°A	1000		Dark	✓		
114859	P2	900	174°A	1000		Scene	✓		
115341	P2	5000	174°A			Interrupt of profile			
115537	P2	5000	174°A			Re-start profile			
115936	P2	9000	174°A			Interrupt of profile			
120205	P2	9000	174°A			Re-start profile			
////	P2		174°A			over 5/8 SCS / Cu 2			
121226	P2	22000	174°A			End of profile			

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 262** Date **25/1/07** Operat or(s) **JEFF BROWN** log page **2** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
121574	R 2	21000	174° A	1000		Start of run	/		
////	R 2			250				/	
	R 2			1000					/
121746	R 2		6°F						
121809	R 2	21000	6°F	500		Dark all	✓		
121821	R 2	21000	6°F	500		Scene all			✓
121954	R 2	21000	6°F	350		Dark SWS	✓		
122003	R 2	21000	6°F	350		Scene SWS	✓		
122729	R 2	21000	6°F	350		Start LSH			✓
122738	R 2	21000	6°F	350		Scene LSH			✓
123046	R 2	21000	6°F			End of run			
123130		21000	174° A			Head to Nadir			
123250			174° A	750		Dark all	✓		
127305			174° A	750		Scene all			✓
123317	R 2.2	21000	174° A						
127425	R 2.2	21000	174° A	250		Dark all	✓	Above 6/9	
123437	R 2.2	21000	174° A	250		Scene all		SWS	✓
123625	R 2.2	21000	174° A	500		Dark all	✓		
123877	R 2.2	21000	174° A	500		Scene all			✓
124000	R 2.2	21000	174° A			Sonde 1 released			
124112	R 3.1	21000	174° A			Start of profile climb			
124711	R 3.1	28000	174° A	200		Dark SWS	✓		
124744	R 3.1	28000	174° A	200		Scene SWS	✓		
	R 3.1	30000	174° A			End of profile			
125534		30000	174° A	100		SWS Dark	✓		
125543		30000	174° A	100		SWS Scene	✓		
125653		30000	174° A	300		LSH Dark			✓
125702		30000	174° A	300		LSH Scene			✓
125805		30000	174° A	350		SWS Dark			
125812		30000	174° A	350		SWS Scene			
125945	R 3.2	30000	174° A			Start of run			
130350		30000	174° A			Moved head to check for freezing - back to Nadir			
131243	P 4	30000	174° A			End of run / start of climb			
131601	P 4	32000	174° A			Interrupt profile			
131700	P 4 (5)	32000	174° A			Start of profile			
131830	P 4 (5)	33000	174° A			End of profile			
132241	P 6	33000	174° A			Start of profile			
132355	P 6	34000	174° A			End of profile			
132428		34000	174° A	200		SWS Dark	✓		
132437		34000	174° A	200		SWS Scene	✓		
132507	P 9	34000	174° A			Start of profile			
132740	P 9	35000	174° A			End of profile + start of run			
133007		35000	174° A			Sonde 2 dropped			
						Sonde 3 dropped			
1345		35000	6°F			Head on Zenith (took 15 mins)			
134653		35000	6°F	750			✓		
134708		35000	6°F	750			✓		
1350						SWS head from solid - 64°C			
135235	P 9	35000	6°F			Start of profile			
140402				350		AN dark	✓		

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 262** Date **25/1/07** Operat or(s) **JGFF BROWN** log page **3** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

140440		23000	6° TA F	1000		Scene all			✓
140831		20000	6° AF			End of profile			
1410		20000	6° BF			SWS head moveable			
141200		20000	6° AF	750		USH Dark			✓
141240				750		USH Scene			✓
141358	P24	20000				Profile climb			
141550		22300	174° A			SWS head to Nadir			
141638		24000	174° A	1000		SWS Dark	✓		
141712		24000	174° A	1000		SWS Scene	✓		
141825		25900	174° A	500		SWS Dark	✓		
141834		25900	174° A	500		SWS Scene	✓		
142133		33600	174° A	400		USH DARK			✓
142751		33600	174° A	400		USH Scene			✓
143036	P9 / P10	35000	174° A			End of profile / Start of Profile			
143600		30000	6° F						
144210		22600	6° F	1000		Dark all	✓		
144226		22600	6° F	750		Scene all			✓
144455		20500	6° F	750		SWS Dark	✓		
144504		20500	6° F	750		SWS Scene	✓		
144522	P10 / P11	20000	6° F			End of profile / Start of profile			
144959	R6	24000	6° F			End of profile / Start of run			
145054		24000	6° F	500		USH DARK			✓
145101		24000	6° F	500		USH Scene			✓
145410		24000	6° F	500		USH DARK			✓
145420		24000	6° F	500		USH Scene			✓
150524		24000	6° F	1000		SWS DARK	✓		
150538		24000	6° F	1000		SWS Scene	✓		
150756		End of run - end of science							

ARIES flight log

Flight: B202

page 1 of

Date: 25/1/06

Operator(s): Joss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CIRRUS - East Coast Scotland

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
							<u>START asci Nowee keeping 0911</u>
		<u>HBB = 70°</u>					
		<u>CBB = 300</u>					
<u>09157</u>	<u>Cond</u>	<u>1x120</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>71.06</u>	<u>30.94</u>	<u>For inflight cal</u>
<u>095307</u>	<u>Cond</u>	<u>1x120</u>	<u>CBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>71.48</u>	<u>31.34</u>	<u>For inflight cal</u>
<u>102001</u>	<u>FLISO</u>	<u>1x120</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.47</u>	<u>30.14</u>	<u>For inflight cal</u>
<u>102118</u>	<u>FLISO</u>	<u>1x120</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>			
<u>110649</u>	<u>FL190</u>	<u>1x120</u>	<u>CBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.71</u>	<u>30.48</u>	<u>In transit</u>
<u>110759</u>	<u>FL190</u>	<u>1x120</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.68</u>	<u>30.89</u>	
<u>110903</u>	<u>FL190</u>	<u>1x120</u>	<u>Zen</u>	<u>open</u>	<u>70.6</u>	<u>30.79</u>	
<u>111107</u>	<u>FL190</u>	<u>1x120</u>	<u>Wod</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.7</u>	<u>31.04</u>	
<u>112959</u>	<u>1000'</u>	<u>120x1</u>	<u>CBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.77</u>	<u>30.59</u>	
<u>113112</u>	<u>500'</u>	<u>120x1</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.7</u>	<u>30.59</u>	
<u>113239</u>	<u>100'</u>	<u>360x1</u>	<u>NAD</u>	<u>clsd</u>			
<u>133626</u>	<u>100'</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>CBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>			
<u>113718</u>	<u>100'</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>			
<u>114005</u>	<u>113828</u>	<u>100'</u>	<u>NAD</u>	<u>clsd</u>			<u>oops - didnt store acquisition</u>
<u>114245</u>	<u>100'</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>CBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.8</u>	<u>30.74</u>	
<u>114352</u>	<u>100'</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.73</u>	<u>30.58</u>	
<u>114522</u>	<u>100'</u>	<u>240</u>	<u>Zen</u>	<u>open</u>			
<u>114734</u>	<u>100'</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>CBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.92</u>	<u>30.64</u>	
<u>114840</u>	<u>100'</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>71.19</u>	<u>30.73</u>	<u>State profile up.</u>
<u>121229</u>	<u>220</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>			
<u>121334</u>	<u>220</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>CBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.61</u>	<u>30.35</u>	
<u>121619</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.76</u>	<u>30.27</u>	
<u>121722</u>	<u>FL120</u>	<u>480</u>	<u>Zen</u>	<u>open</u>	<u>69.88</u>	<u>31.15</u>	<u>Run 2</u>
<u>121729</u>	<u>R2 FL20</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>CBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.36</u>	<u>31.01</u>	<u>Run 2</u>
<u>122410</u>	<u>R2 FL120</u>	<u>480</u>	<u>Zen</u>	<u>open</u>	<u>70.37</u>	<u>30.42</u>	
<u>122811</u>	<u>R2 FL20</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>CBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>69.96</u>	<u>30.39</u>	
<u>122927</u>	<u>R2 FL120</u>	<u>120</u>	<u>HBB</u>	<u>clsd</u>	<u>70.91</u>	<u>29.88</u>	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B262

page 2 of

Date: 25/1/06

Operator(s): Doss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
123301	R2-2	120x1	CIB	Clsd	7066	3044	FL210
123406	R2-2	120x1	HBB	Clsd	7043	3055	FL210
123525	R2-2	480x1	Nwd	Clsd	7065	3040	FL210
123952	R2-2	480x1	Nwd	Clsd	7069	3046	FL210 finished early
124048	R2-2	120x1	CIB	Clsd	7074	3055	FL210
124155	R2-2	120x1	HBB	Clsd	7065	31-14	FL210
125457		120x1	CIB	Clsd	7064	30-24	
125556	FL310	120x1	HBB	Clsd	7065	30-42	
125800	FL300	480x1	Nwd	Clsd	7034	30-65	
130305	FL300	120x1	CIB	Clsd	7060	30-04	
132623	T-345	120x1	HBB	Clsd			
132734	FL350	120x1	CIB	Clsd	7052	3046	
132848	FL350	480x1	NAD	Clsd	7064	3062	slightly in Cirrus cloud top
133300	FL350	120x1	CIB	Clsd			
133416	FL350	120x1	HBB	Clsd	7043	3038	
133501	FL350	240x1	Zen	open	7093	7011	In slight turn.
134023	FL350	240x1	Zen	open	7039	3049	Again in slight turn
134241	FL350	120x1	CIB	Clsd	7058	3034	
134415	FL350	240x1	HBB	Clsd			
134415	FL350	240x1	Zen	open	7051	2964	
134655	FL350	920x1	Zen	open	7040	3004	
134701	FL350	240x1	Nwd	Clsd	7039	2980	
135135	FL350	120x1	CIB	Clsd	7059	3006	
135237	FL350	120x1	HBB	Clsd	7055	3030	
135652		120x1	CIB	Clsd	7052	3057	
135559		120x1	HBB	Clsd	7039	3042	
135914		480x1	NAD	Clsd	7049	3017	
140435		120x1	CIB	Clsd	7039	3020	
140540		120x1	HBB	Clsd	7041	3100	
140655		480x1	NAD	Clsd	7062	3019	140948 banking.
141110		240x1	CIB	open	6997	2996	some manoeuvring

Zen

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	25/01/07	Flight	B262	log pages
Operator(s)	Chawn Harlow		Campaign	WINTEX		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	New Castle/Cranfield		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						•	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•	
FERA on					at time	0830	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on					at time	0830	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating						•	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•	
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	0830	
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							
Turn on Deimos CPU							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software					at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$		at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	345	Cold	276	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
		32.4	37.6	40.2	42.4	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	

Flight:

B262

KEY

- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated
- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turbulence Check Press:
- Turbulence Diff Press:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:

- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3010A:
- INC:
- VACC:

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Report Created 05/02/2007 11:36:25

Last Updated:

25/01/2007 17:45:47

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B262

Date: 25th January 2007

Instruments

1. Cruciform GPS – u/s
2. TW sample temperature over limit, one heater switched off – Ignore all data
3. PCASP noise caused by SWS motor drive
4. SWS unable to switch between zenith and nadir below –60C
5. 2dp noisy
6. TAFTS data not wonderful

Aircraft

Interference on intercom still present

Satcom H Calls

None

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B262:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Electronic processing log is corrupt therefore not available
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
FWVS	No log is ever taken for FWVS
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Phil Brown

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	15 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Rearward Facing Cameras
2 x Downward Facing Cameras
1 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647
Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk